

PEDAGOGICAL HERITAGE OF GREAT EDUCATORS AND ITS
INFLUENCE ON MODERN EDUCATIONAL SYSTEMS (COMENIUS,
PESTALOZZI AND USHINSKY)

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Annotation: The article is dedicated to the study of the pedagogical heritage of the greatest educators of all the time, such as, Johann Heinrich Pestalozzi, Amos Comenius and Konstantin Dmitrievich Ushinsky, who had a huge impact on modern educational systems. The main pedagogical ideas and principles proposed by these thinkers are considered, such as accessibility of education for everyone, the usage of visual materials, attentiveness to the age characteristics of students, the development of moral values and civic responsibility. The articles analyses how these ideas continue to be implemented into educational practices in the 21st century through innovative teaching methods such as inclusive education, project-based learning, patriotic education and socio-emotional development.

Key words: education, pedagogy, pedagogical, development, implementation, teaching, approaches

The pedagogy itself and its history are rich in great scientists and educators, whose legacy had a significant impact on the development of educational systems. They are implemented all the world around in various educational institution systems. In this context, the figures of Jan Amos Comenius, Johann Heinrich Pestalozzi and Konstantin Dmitrievich Ushinsky are the key to shaping the foundations of modern pedagogy. These educators not only created the theoretical approaches that were used in their era, but also laid the foundation for the methods and principles that are actively used in education today.

John Amos Comenius and his influence in educational systems. Jan Amos Comenius, an outstanding Czech teacher, writer, great thinker and public figure of the 17th century, and he is the founder of scientific pedagogy, made a great contribution to the development of pedagogical science. He is the author of many philosophical and pedagogical works imbued with the spirit of humanism, love and respect for people, for their work. J.A Comenius preached the idea of eliminating class privileges and oppression of man by man, advocated boundless love for the Motherland, faith in a bright future, for the equality of all peoples and respect for the national rights of each them. He was a fighter for ending all

wars and restoring peace throughout the world. The great merit of J.A Comenius to mankind is that he was able to give a critical assessment of the entire obsolete medieval education system. Taking into account all the valuable things that his predecessors had accumulated, he created a pedagogical teaching that remains relevant to this day.

He had created the first scientific theory of teaching in the history of pedagogy, didactics, subordinated to the idea of comprehensive personality development. The main work of his life is the Universal Council for the Correction of Human Affairs (1643-1670), consisting of 7 parts, in which he outlined a clear concept of the transformation of human society. Unfortunately, he never managed to complete this work during his lifetime. Furthermore, The Great Didactics (1633-1638) is considered to be the most influential and central work of him in pedagogical theory. Conceived in his youth, it has been nurtured for many years, overgrown with various additions and applications. The full title reads as follows: "The Great didactics, which contains the universal art of teaching everyone everything, or a sure and carefully thought-out way to create schools in all communities, towns and villages of every Christian state in which all youth of one gender or another, without any exception, could be taught sciences, to improve in morals, to be filled with piety, and thus in the years of youth to learn everything that is necessary for present and future life".

According to his opinion, pedagogical activity is one of the most important public affairs and should be strongly supported by a public organization. The school should have "a sufficient stock of pan-methodological books" [2, p.471], the preparation of which requires the association of "talented and unafraid scholars" [2, p.472]. This methodical work should be generously paid for by school patrons.

Johann Heinrich Pestalozzi. Johannes Heinrich Pestalozzi (1746-1827), Swiss educator and reformer, also had a significant impact on the development of pedagogy in Europe and the world. He opposed traditional teaching methods, such as rigorous memorization, and offered a new understanding of the learning process, focusing on the holistic development of the child's personality. The main idea of Pestalozzi was education through experience and practical activity. He believed that education should be aimed at developing not only intellectual abilities, but also the emotional, social and physical components of a person.

He had developed a methodology aimed at developing intuitive knowledge in children. He believed that children should learn through direct interaction with the outside world, through sensations and perception. This idea continues

to live on in modern pedagogical approaches such as learning through activity, project-based learning, and collaborative pedagogy. Moreover, the main purpose of education, according to Pestalozzi, is not to provide only knowledge, but also to draw students' attention to the contemplation of the world, thereby awakening their consciousness, thinking and deepening their impressions. The main aim of education is to develop logical thinking.

K. D. Ushinsky and his influence on Russian pedagogy. Konstantin Dmitrievich Ushinsky (1824-1870), the founder of scientific pedagogy in Russia, made a significant contribution to the development of Russian education. Ushinsky believed that pedagogy should be a strictly scientific discipline based on the study of the nature of the child and society. He raised issues of upbringing and education, drawing attention to the importance of moral education and the formation of a civic position among students. Ushinsky also emphasized the importance of national education. He believed that education should be focused on the development of national identity and love for the Motherland. This has become the basis for the development of curricula that include elements of patriotic education and civic responsibility.

He had adhered and consistently developed various ideas regarding pedagogy:

- Education should be compulsory for everyone, regardless of class. Women have the same right to education as men (recall that Ushinsky came to pedagogy even before the abolition of serfdom, and women in the Russian Empire fought for equal rights to education until the 1917 revolution, so these ideas were way ahead of their time);
- Pedagogy cannot rely solely on the personal experience of the teacher, because he may be mistaken. It should be based on theory, that is, a comprehensive study of a person and a systematic experience. Therefore, pedagogical ideas should be developed at the university, based on science;
- The main aim of pedagogy should be fostering morality, not providing only knowledge. The school should prepare a person for life and work;
- Learning is not mechanical cramming, but the development of the student's mental abilities, observation, imagination, imagination, desire and the ability to further acquire knowledge on their own. Learning should be conscious, that is, students need to be informed why they are learning and what they will eventually learn.

Conclusion

The ideas of Comenius, Pestalozzi, and Ushinsky continue to influence modern educational systems. It is important to note that the pedagogical heritage of these thinkers is integrated into educational practice through such modern concepts as inclusive education, socio-emotional learning, as well as a differentiated approach to learning. For instance, schools around the world are actively using visual materials, games and project technologies, and comprehensive models are actively being developed aimed at getting all children involved in the educational process, regardless of their abilities.

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